

How do Exercise Referral Schemes impact participant healthcare resource utilisation and health-related outcomes? A Rapid evidence summary

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Abstract: The National Exercise Referral Scheme (NERS) was rolled out across Wales in 2012. It is a long-term condition prevention and management programme, which aims to improve the health and well-being of sedentary and inactive adults who are at risk of developing a long-term condition or who have an existing long-term condition.

This Rapid Evidence Summary (RES) was conducted as part of an ongoing economic evaluation of NERS in Wales. The RES aimed to evaluate the impacts that Exercise Referral Schemes (ERSs) have had on participant healthcare resource utilisation (HCRU) and health-related outcomes. The searches included evidence published from January 2000 to November 2025. Eleven evidence sources were identified.

Key Findings:

- The influence of ERSs on HCRU was only reported in 1 study. In this study, the ERS was not effective in reducing HCRU compared to a control group.
- Evidence on the effectiveness of ERSs on participant physical activity levels was mixed. Evidence suggested ERSs were effective in increasing physical activity often reported only marginal improvements compared to usual care.
- Impact on Health-related quality of life (HRQoL) was assessed in 2 studies by reporting change in Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALY). ERSs were effective in improving QALYs, however QALY gains were modest across both studies.
- Identified evidence of ERS impacts on mental health and wellbeing suggests ERSs were effective in improving depression, anxiety and stress outcomes in participants, but these changes were not statistically significant in two studies.
- For outcomes around 'condition(s)/disease(s) avoided/risk factor(s) modified', the evidence was mixed, with one review reporting the ERS was effective in decreasing blood pressure amongst participants with cardiovascular disorders, while another review found ERS did not improve anthropometric, physiological or biochemical outcomes. An umbrella review of meta-analyses suggested that improvement in physical activity and aerobic fitness could lead to a reduced risk of experiencing a major adverse cardiovascular event.

From the limited evidence identified, ERSs were not effective in reducing participant HCRU. As a mechanism aimed to solely reduce HCRU, ERSs alone may not be the most effective option. However, ERSs were found to be effective in generating improvements in participant physical activity, HRQoL and blood pressure outcomes. Increasing provision of ERS in Wales for those living with or at risk of developing long-term health conditions may contribute to the better management of conditions or risk factors through ERSs.

HCRU was the least reported outcome within the identified evidence. Future investigation of the effectiveness of ERSs in changing HCRU of participants is warranted.

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How do Exercise Referral Schemes impact participant healthcare resource utilisation and health-related outcomes: a rapid evidence summary

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How do Exercise Referral Schemes impact participant healthcare resource utilisation and health-related outcomes? A Rapid evidence summary

Executive Summary

Report number RES0052 (February 2026)

What is a Rapid Evidence Summary?

Our Rapid Evidence Summaries (RES) are designed to provide a rapid response product. They are based on a limited search of key resources and the assessment of abstracts. Priority is given to studies representing robust evidence synthesis. No quality appraisal is conducted, and the summary should be interpreted with caution.

Who is this Rapid Evidence Summary for?

The research question was submitted by a public health consultant and members of the National Exercise Referral Scheme (NERS) team at Public Health Wales.

Background / Aim of Rapid Evidence Summary

The National Exercise Referral Scheme (NERS) was developed in 2007/2008, and in 2010 the scheme was formally evaluated using randomised controlled trial (RCT) methodology and scaled up following the RCT. NERS is a Welsh Government-funded scheme which is centrally managed by Public Health Wales (PHW) and delivered in the 22 local authority areas of Wales. It is a long-term condition prevention and management programme which aims to improve the health and well-being of sedentary and inactive adults who are at risk of developing a long-term condition or who have an existing long-term condition.

This Rapid Evidence Summary was conducted as **part of an economic evaluation of NERS in Wales**, which aims to address the following research questions:

- What is the return on investment for the National Exercise Referral Scheme (NERS) in Wales for the management of chronic health conditions?
- What is the direct cost of NERS versus the long-term societal benefits and potential cost savings to the health service from the intervention on managing and improving health and other outcomes for those with chronic conditions?

Generating evidence on the return on investment of NERS would build on the existing evidence base of its clinical and cost-effectiveness. This evidence would facilitate decision-making in Welsh Government around wider investment in NERS. Greater provision in Wales for those living with or at risk of developing long-term health conditions that could be managed through exercise programmes, could also deliver benefits through reducing demands on primary and secondary health services.

This rapid evidence summary aimed to evaluate the impacts that Exercise Referral Schemes (ERSs) have had on participant healthcare resource utilisation (HCRU) and health-related outcomes. Literature searches and references provided by stakeholders were used.

Results

Recency and extent of the evidence base

- The searches included evidence published from January 2000 to November 2025 (date of latest search).
- In total, eleven evidence sources were identified, three of which were published since November 2020. Older evidence was published in 2018, 2015, 2011 and 2007.
- The eleven sources included eight secondary sources of evidence: six systematic reviews (SRs) – of which two had an embedded economic evaluation, and one was a review of economic evaluations only; one umbrella review of meta-analyses; and one secondary analysis of two randomised controlled trials (RCTs).
- Within the secondary sources of evidence, the publication dates of studies ranged from 1998 to 2022.
- One UK clinical guideline for ERSs was identified, published by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence in 2014.
- Two primary studies evaluating NERS in Wales were included, analysing the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of participants recruited between 2007 and 2008.

Key findings

- Healthcare resource utilisation (HCRU): The influence of ERSs on HCRU was only reported in 1 study (secondary analysis of 2 RCTs), with two other studies reporting primary economic evaluations that considered HCRU. In the study reporting HCRU, the ERS was **not effective** in reducing HCRU (GP contacts or days hospitalised) compared to a control group.
- Physical Activity: Evidence on the effectiveness of ERSs on participant physical activity levels was mixed. Evidence suggesting ERSs were effective in increasing physical activity often reported only **marginal improvements** compared to usual care.
- Health-related quality of life (HRQoL): Impact on HRQoL was assessed in 2 studies by reporting change in Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALY). ERSs were effective in improving QALYs, however **QALY gains were modest** across both studies.
- Mental health and wellbeing: Identified evidence of ERS impacts on mental health and wellbeing suggests ERSs were effective in improving depression, anxiety and stress outcomes in participants, but these changes were **not statistically significant** in two studies.
- Condition(s)/disease(s) avoided/risk factor(s) modified: **Evidence in these outcome areas was mixed**, with one review reporting the **ERS was effective in decreasing blood pressure amongst participants with cardiovascular disorders**, while another review found **ERS did not improve anthropometric, physiological or biochemical outcomes**. An umbrella review of meta-analyses suggested that improvement in physical activity and aerobic fitness could lead to a reduced risk of experiencing a major adverse cardiovascular event.

Policy and Practice Implications

- From the limited evidence base identified, ERSs were not effective in reducing participant HCRU. As a mechanism aimed to solely reduce HCRU, ERSs alone may not be the most effective option.
- However, ERSs were found to be effective in generating improvements in participant physical activity, HRQoL and blood pressure outcomes.
- Increasing provision of ERS in Wales for those living with or at risk of developing long-term health conditions may contribute to the better management of conditions or risk factors through ERSs.

Research Implications and Evidence Gaps

- HCRU was the least reported outcome within identified evidence. Future investigation of the effectiveness of ERSs in changing HCRU of participants is warranted.

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Full Description
ERS	Exercise Referral Scheme
HCRU	Healthcare Resource Utilisation
HRQoL	Health-related quality of life
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
NERS	National Exercise Referral Scheme
NICE	National Institute for health and Care Excellence
QALY	Quality Adjusted Life Year
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
RES	Rapid Evidence Summary
ROI	Return on Investment

Glossary

Economic evaluation: An assessment of the costs and effects of alternate healthcare interventions. The aim of an economic evaluation is to help decision makers maximise the level of health benefits relative to the finite healthcare resources available.

Exercise Referral Scheme (ERS): Exercise Referral Schemes are typically short-term, supervised, programmes of physical activity, that aim to encourage participants to both adhere to the physical activity demands of the programme as well as encourage lifestyle changes. Participants can be referred through several mechanisms (such as GP referral) for a variety of medical conditions and/or a history of sedentary lifestyle.

Healthcare resource utilisation (HCRU): HCRU represents the use of healthcare services by patients across the health system such as operations, consultations, medications and medical tests.

Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER): An ICER is a summary measure that represents the economic value of a healthcare intervention when compared with an alternative (comparator). An ICER is calculated by dividing the difference in total costs (incremental cost) by the difference in the chosen measure of health outcome or effect (incremental effect). This yields a ratio of 'extra cost per extra unit of health effort.

Meta-Analysis: A meta-analysis is an evidence synthesis process used to systematically synthesise or merge the findings of single, independent studies using statistical methods to calculate an overall or absolute effect. It extends systematic review methodology through its application of statistical methods.

National Institute for health and Care Excellence (NICE): NICE is an independent body funded by the UK Department of Health and Social Care that develops evidence-based guidance, appraisals, and quality standards to help the NHS and wider health and care system provide high-quality, value-for-money care.

Quality-adjusted life year (QALY): Calculated by aggregating the number of years of life gained from a drug or healthcare intervention, weighted by the relative value attached to the health state (or quality of health) spent in those additional years gained.

Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT): RCTs are a form of scientific experimental design in which an intervention is assessed through the random allocation of participants to one or more comparison groups. One group receives the intervention assessed while the

comparator groups receive standard care or an alternative intervention. The mitigation of bias within RCTs means evidence generated by RCTs is of good quality.

Return on Investment analysis (ROI): ROI is a measure of investment performance that presents the return of a given investment relative to the cost of investment. ROI is calculated by first calculating the return (benefits less cost), then dividing by the cost of the project to generate a percentage. For an ROI analysis, benefits must be expressed in monetary terms to provide an accurate comparison to the cost.

Systematic Review: A systematic review is a type of evidence synthesis in which authors develop explicit eligibility criteria, search for, screen and collect all the available studies that meet these criteria and summarise study results using reproducible methods that minimise biases and errors.

Umbrella Review: An umbrella review, often termed a review of reviews, is a type of evidence synthesis that collates evidence from across systematic reviews or meta-analyses across a topic area to present a holistic overview of associated evidence.

1. CONTEXT / BACKGROUND

1.1. Background and purpose of the review

The National Exercise Referral Scheme (NERS) was developed in 2007/2008 and formally evaluated by a randomised controlled trial in 2010. The intervention was rolled out across Wales in 2012. NERS is a Welsh Government-funded scheme which is centrally managed by Public Health Wales (PHW) and delivered by the 22 local authority areas of Wales. It is a long-term condition prevention and management programme which aims to improve the health and well-being of sedentary and inactive adults who are at risk of developing a long-term condition or who have an existing long-term condition.

This research question received from Public Health Wales concerned a primary evaluation of the National Exercise Referral Scheme (NERS) in Wales. The primary evaluation aims to address the following research questions:

- What is the return on investment for the National Exercise Referral Scheme (NERS) in Wales for the management of chronic health conditions? Assessing the return on investment of the Wales National Exercise Referral Scheme (NERS).
- Evaluate the direct cost of NERS versus the long-term societal benefits and cost savings from the intervention on managing and improving health and other outcomes for those with chronic conditions.

Generating evidence on the return on investment (ROI) of NERS would build on the current evidence base. This evidence would facilitate decision-making in Welsh Government around wider investment in NERS and demonstrate its value, leading to greater provision in Wales for those living with or at risk of developing long-term health conditions that could be managed through exercise programmes, and reducing demands on primary and secondary health services.

Following initial data exploration and discussions with stakeholders and methodologists, it was established there was a need to identify evidence from the literature to inform the healthcare resource utilisation (HCRU) element of the primary evaluation (ROI). Hence this rapid evidence summary was undertaken.

1.2. Research question

The main focus of the evidence review was identifying evidence of the impact of Exercise Referral schemes (ERS) on participant HCRU. The review also included evidence of the impact on health-related outcomes to act as sensitivity analyses within the primary evaluation and to set the evaluation within in a UK-wide perspective. The review question is broken down according to the Population, Intervention/Exposure, Comparison and Outcome (PICO) framework in the table below.

Review question	
How do Exercise Referral Schemes impact participant healthcare resource utilisation and health-related outcomes?	
Participants	Anyone aged 16+.
Intervention / exposure	Any Exercise Referral Scheme (ERS).
Comparison	Any comparator reported (for example: manualised exercise where patients are given exercise instructions, participants who were referred but did not complete the ERS or those not referred or participating in ERS at all).
Outcomes	<p>Primary outcome of interest</p> <p>Healthcare resource utilisation (HCRU)</p> <p>Secondary outcomes of interest</p> <p>Health-related outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of physical activity, • health-related quality of life (HRQoL), • mental health and wellbeing, • condition(s)/disease(s) avoided/risk factors of these modified through ERS.
Other Study Considerations	
<p>Countries: UK (England, Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland) and OECD countries including USA, Australia and European countries.</p> <p>Study design: All comparative study designs (with before and after comparisons)</p> <p>Search dates: 2000 to 2025</p>	

2. SUMMARY OF THE EVIDENCE BASE

2.1. Type and amount of evidence available

- Across primary, secondary and tertiary research, eleven studies were included in total.
- Eight studies were secondary evidence reviews of Exercise Referral Schemes. This included one umbrella review of meta-analyses, six systematic reviews (SR) – of which two had an embedded economic evaluation, and one was a review of economic evaluations only.
- One study was a secondary analysis of two randomised controlled trials (RCTs).
- Two studies generated primary evidence of NERS in Wales (2013, 2012). These primary studies were known to the research team before the inception of this Rapid Evidence Summary.
- One clinical guideline for ERS' was identified, published by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) in 2014.
- Of the eight secondary evidence reviews identified, three were published in the last 5 years (since Nov 2020). Older evidence was published in 2018, 2015, 2011 and

2007. Within secondary sources of evidence, the publication dates ranged from 1998 to 2022.

3. KEY FINDINGS

3.1. Healthcare Resource Utilisation (HCRU)

Effectiveness of Exercise Referral Schemes in influencing participant HCRU was only reported in one study, with two other studies reporting primary economic evaluations that considered Healthcare resource utilisation. In the study reporting healthcare resource utilisation, neither an Exercise Referral Scheme plus Self-Management Strategy nor the Exercise Referral Scheme standalone interventions were effective in reducing healthcare resource utilisation over a 2-year follow-up period compared to the Self-Management Strategy alone. No statistically significant between-groups differences were found regarding GP contacts or days hospitalised. Review of healthcare resource utilisation in economic evaluations reported in secondary evidence will supplement these findings.

3.2. Physical Activity

Seven studies considered the effectiveness of Exercise Referral Schemes on change in participant physical activity. Evidence of effectiveness on participant physical activity levels was mixed. Evidence suggesting Exercise Referral Schemes were effective in increasing physical activity often reported only moderate improvements compared to usual care. Primary economic evaluations of Exercise Referral Schemes presented in the secondary evidence sources used steps per day, level of reported walking and the proportion of participants reporting being active as incremental benefits in their evaluations.

3.3. Health-related quality of life (HRQoL)

Three studies considered the effectiveness of Exercise Referral Schemes in improving HRQoL through reporting change in Quality Adjusted Life Year (QALY). One Systematic Review reported Exercise Referral Schemes were cost-effective when an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio was calculated using QALYs as the outcome measure in four primary study examples. Another Systematic Review reported an Exercise Referral Scheme was effective in improving health-related quality of life through reporting a mean gain of 0.003 QALYs. A third Systematic Review presented modest QALY gains across studies. The review reported the highest QALY gain across included primary studies was 0.079.

3.4. Mental health and wellbeing

Identified evidence on the effectiveness of Exercise Referral Schemes on improving participant mental health and wellbeing suggests depression, anxiety and stress outcomes improved, but these changes were not statistically significant in two studies. In one Systematic Review, participants referred to an Exercise Referral Scheme for mental health reasons had improved depression, anxiety and stress outcomes when assessed at a longer follow-up period. In another Systematic Review, one included primary economic evaluation used anxiety as measure of incremental benefit.

3.5. Condition(s)/disease(s) avoided/risk factor(s) modified

Two Systematic Reviews considered modification of risk factors in Exercise Referral Scheme participants. One suggested that an Exercise Referral Scheme was effective in

reducing blood pressure in patients referred with cardiovascular disorders. Another found Exercise Referral Schemes were not effective in influencing anthropometric, physiological or biochemical outcomes between exercise groups and controls, suggesting any improvements in these outcomes was mirrored by similar improvement in control groups. One umbrella review suggested that improvements in physical activity and aerobic fitness due to participating in an Exercise Referral Scheme, likely translated to a reduced risk of experiencing a major adverse cardiovascular event.

3.6. Areas of uncertainty

The **primary** remaining uncertainty pertinent to the primary evaluation is:

- The influence Exercise Referral Schemes have on healthcare resource utilisation.

However, the lack of reporting suggests the evaluation of the effect Exercise Referral Schemes have on healthcare resource utilisation has not been explored widely.

4. NEXT STEPS

The evidence identified in this Rapid Evidence Summary will be used to supplement the planned primary evaluation of NERS. It is suggested the review team investigate key primary evidence sources (economic evaluations) to determine the extent to which participant HCRU is influenced by Exercise Referral Schemes.

This is a suggested next step as evidence on the influence Exercise Referral Schemes have on healthcare resource utilisation and health-related outcomes will be used to inform pro-rated estimation of such impacts of NERS in Wales.

5. REFERENCES

Campbell F, Holmes M, Everson-Hock E, Davis S, Buckley Woods H, Anokye N, Tappenden P, Kaltenthaler E. A systematic review and economic evaluation of exercise referral schemes in primary care: a short report. *Health Technol Assess.* 2015 Jul;19(60):1-110. doi: 10.3310/hta19600. PMID: 26222987; PMCID: PMC4781341.

National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE).2014. NICE Public health guideline: PH54: Physical activity: exercise referral schemes

O'Brien MW, Shivgulam M, Liu H, Courish M, Wu Y, Fowles J, Nagpal T. The effectiveness of exercise referral schemes on patient health and their cost: an umbrella review. *Appl Physiol Nutr Metab.* 2025 Jan 1;50:1-12. doi: 10.1139/apnm-2024-0185. PMID: 39693607.

Pavey TG, Anokye N, Taylor AH, Trueman P, Moxham T, Fox KR, Hillsdon M, Green C, Campbell JL, Foster C, Mutrie N, Searle J, Taylor RS. The clinical effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of exercise referral schemes: a systematic review and economic evaluation. *Health Technol Assess.* 2011 Dec;15(44):i-xii, 1-254. doi: 10.3310/hta15440. PMID: 22182828; PMCID: PMC4781450.

Rowley, N., Mann, S., Steele, J. et al. The effects of exercise referral schemes in the United Kingdom in those with cardiovascular, mental health, and musculoskeletal disorders: a preliminary systematic review. *BMC Public Health* 18, 949 (2018). doi: 10.1186/s12889-018-5868-9

Svensson NH, Thorlund JB, Øllgaard Olsen P, et al Effect of exercise referral schemes and self-management strategies on healthcare service utilisation among community-dwelling older adults: secondary analyses of two randomised controlled trials *BMJ Open* 2024;14:e084938. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2024-084938

Tomlinson-Perez, S., Machaczek, K.K., Firth, J. et al. Evaluation of the uptake, retention and effectiveness of exercise referral schemes for the management of mental health conditions in primary care: a systematic review. *BMC Public Health* 22, 249 (2022). doi: 10.1186/s12889-022-12638-7

Werbrouck A, Schmidt M, Putman K, Seghers J, Simoens S, Verhaeghe N, Annemans L. Cost-effectiveness of exercise referral schemes: a systematic review of health economic studies. *Eur J Public Health.* 2022 Feb 1;32(1):87-94. doi: 10.1093/eurpub/ckab189. PMID: 34864937; PMCID: PMC9090165.

Williams NH, Hendry M, France B, Lewis R, Wilkinson C. Effectiveness of exercise-referral schemes to promote physical activity in adults: systematic review. *Br J Gen Pract.* 2007 Dec;57(545):979-86. doi: 10.3399/096016407782604866. PMID: 18252074; PMCID: PMC2084138.

6. RAPID EVIDENCE SUMMARY METHODS

A list of the resources searched during Rapid Evidence Summary is provided within the Appendix 1. Searches were limited to English-language publications and did not include searches for primary studies if secondary research relevant to the question was found. Search hits were screened for relevance by a single reviewer.

Priority was given to robust evidence synthesis using minimum standards (systematic search, study selection, quality assessment, appropriate synthesis). The secondary research identified was not retrieved as full text or formally quality assessed. The included research may vary considerably in quality, and the degree of such variation could be investigated during rapid review work which may follow-on. Citation, recency, evidence type, document status and key findings were tabulated for all relevant secondary research identified in this process.

Date of Search	October/November 2025
Search Concepts Used	Exercise Referral Scheme(s) Healthcare Resource Utilisation (HCRU) HRQoL/QoL/QALY Economic Evaluation
Search Completed by	Centre for Health Economics and Medicines Evaluation

7. EVIDENCE

Table 1. Summary of review evidence identified

Evidence type	Total identified	Comments
Systematic reviews (SRs)	3	One focused on mental health referrals only, another on cardiovascular, mental health, and musculoskeletal disorders. One focused on impact of physical activity
Clinical Guidelines (CGs)	1	NICE Public health guideline: PH54: Physical activity: exercise referral schemes
SRs with embedded Economic Evaluation	2	Both aimed to assess clinical and cost-effectiveness of ERS.
Primary economic evaluation (EE)	1	EE of NERS, Edwards et al., 2013
Primary Studies	1	RCT of NERS
Umbrella Review of meta-analyses	1	Reported on ERS influence on physical activity, physical and mental health and brief overview of economic evaluations.
Secondary Analysis of two RCTs	1	Assessed whether ERS or ERS combined with self-management strategy was more effective than control at reducing HCRU.

A more detailed summary of included evidence can be found in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2: Summary of included secondary evidence

Secondary research						
Resource	Citation	Search date	Evidence Type*	Status**	Key findings	Reviewer comments
Google	<i>Pavey et al (2011). The clinical effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of exercise referral schemes: a systematic review and economic evaluation. Health Technol Assess; doi: 10.3310/hta15440</i>	14/10/2025	SR and EE	Published	<p>There was weak evidence of an increase in the number of ERS participants who achieved a self-reported 90-150 minutes of at least moderate-intensity physical activity per week at 6-12 months' follow up compared with usual care. There was no consistent evidence of a difference between ERS and usual care in the duration of moderate/vigorous intensity and total physical activity or other outcomes.</p> <p>The four economic evaluations identified suggested ERSs to be a cost-effective intervention. The base-case incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) was estimated at £20,876 per quality-adjusted life year (QALY) in sedentary people without medical condition and a cost per QALY gain of £14,618 in sedentary obese individuals, £12,834 in sedentary hypertensive patients, and £8,414 for sedentary individuals with depression.</p>	No consideration of healthcare resource utilisation (HCRU) in the economic evaluation.
Google	<i>Campbell et al (2015). A systematic review and economic evaluation of exercise referral schemes in primary care: a short report. Health Technol Assess; doi:10.3310/hta19600</i>	14/10/25	SR and EE	Published	<p>The proportion of individuals achieving 90-150 minutes of at least moderate-intensity activity per week at 6-12 months' follow up was greater for ERSs than usual care. Older patients and those referred for coronary heart disease risk factors appeared to be more likely than others to increase their levels of physical activity.</p>	<p>This paper updated the evidence presented in Pavey et al. (2011).</p> <p>No consideration of HCRU in the economic evaluation as was the case in Pavey et al. (2011).</p>

					Exercise referral participants gained 0.003 QALYs at an additional cost of £225 per person, resulting in an estimated ICER of £76,276 in the probabilistic sensitivity analysis. The cost-effectiveness of ERSs was uncertain.	
Google	Rowley et al (2018). <i>The effects of exercise referral schemes in the United Kingdom in those with cardiovascular, mental health, and musculoskeletal disorders: a preliminary systematic review.</i> BMC Public Health; doi:10.1186/s12889-018-5868-9	14/10/2025	SR	Published	Longer length schemes (20+ weeks) produced better health outcomes, and had higher adherence to physical activity prescribed, than those of shorter length (8-12 weeks). Cardiovascular-related measures showed significant decreases including blood pressure in patients referred with cardiovascular disorders. The physical activity levels increased regardless of the length of scheme across all disorders.	Mentions relationship between cardiovascular, mental health, and musculoskeletal disorders and GP attendances but does not formally present any evidence of ERS influence on HCRU outcomes.
Google	Svensson et al (2024). <i>Effect of exercise referral schemes and self-management strategies on healthcare service utilisation among community-dwelling older adults: secondary analyses of two randomised controlled trials.</i> BMJ Open; doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2024-084938	14/10/2025	Secondary analysis of 2 RCTs	Published	Neither the ERS plus Self-Management Strategy (SMS) nor the ERS alone intervention was more effective in reducing healthcare service utilisation during 2-year follow-up period compared with a stand-alone SMS/control intervention. No statistically significant between-group differences were found in term of the annual number of days with contact with General Practitioner (GP) and days hospitalised when comparing the ERS+SMS or ERS only group to the SMS/control group.	Conducted assessment of (all cause) GP contacts and days spent hospitalised (all cause) using data from the Danish National Health Service Register and the Danish National Patient Register. <i>[Similar to approach we are taking with SAIL linkage].</i> More detailed methods: <i>“Baseline number of days with contact with GP and days hospitalised was calculated using data from 360 days before the index date (day -361 to -1). The index date was included in the 2-year follow-up period (days 0–720), with months defined as 30-day intervals. Individuals were not excluded in the event of death or migration during</i>

						<i>the follow-up period. Instead, we estimated the time at risk for each individual, which we accounted for in the analyses”.</i>
PROSPERO	O'Brien MW, Shivgulam M, Liu H, Courish M, Wu Y, Fowles J, Nagpal T. The effectiveness of exercise referral schemes on patient health and their cost: an umbrella review . <i>Appl Physiol Nutr Metab</i> . 2025 Jan 1;50:1-12. doi: 10.1139/apnm-2024-0185. PMID: 39693607.	04/11/2025	Umbrella review of MAs	Published	<p>The review indicates that more recent summarisations of evidence observe an improvement in physical activity as well as aerobic fitness, which likely translates to a reduced risk of experiencing a major adverse cardiovascular event and may combat the decrease in fitness.</p> <p>More recent reviews of ERSs demonstrate that these models improve patients' physical activity, physical fitness, depression, and cardiometabolic health, but their cost compared to usual care is not well characterised.</p>	<p>Reported on ERS influence on physical activity, physical and mental health and brief overview of economic evaluations. No consideration of HCRU in synthesis but could look at individual studies to assess this.</p> <p>References of interest: Pavey et al., 2011a Pavey et al., 2011b</p>
Epistemonikos	Tomlinson-Perez, S., Machaczek, K.K., Firth, J. et al. Evaluation of the uptake, retention and effectiveness of exercise referral schemes for the management of mental health conditions in primary care: a systematic review . <i>BMC Public Health</i> 22, 249 (2022). https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-12638-7	04/11/2025	SR	Published	<p>Uptake and effectiveness of ERSs for mental health conditions was related to programme content and setting with more effective programmes providing both face-to-face and telephone consultations.</p> <p>The short-term symptom improvement (depression, anxiety, stress) in ERS groups involving regular face-to-face consultations and telephone calls was not significant. Long-term improvement in symptoms for those taking part in leisure centre-based ERSs was statistically significant, however, it is important to emphasise this is based on the findings of a single study.</p> <p>Only two studies, both Randomised Controlled Trials (RCT), measured the impact of ERSs on long-term physical activity levels in participants referred for</p>	<p>Provides evidence of clinical effectiveness of ERS' on mental health symptoms in patients referred for mental health reasons.</p> <p>Also assessed the effects of ERSs on long-term physical activity levels in participants referred for mental health reasons.</p> <p>Helpful as solely focused on mental health but did not identify economic evidence or HCRU (outside of review scope).</p>

					mental health reasons. Regular face-to-face consultations and telephone calls seemed to be more effective at increasing physical activity levels after 12 months than the leisure centre-based ERS.	
Health Evidence	Werbrouck A, Schmidt M, Putman K, Seghers J, Simoens S, Verhaeghe N, Annemans L. Cost-effectiveness of exercise referral schemes: a systematic review of health economic studies . Eur J Public Health. 2022 Feb 1;32(1):87-94. doi: 10.1093/eurpub/ckab189. PMID: 34864937; PMCID: PMC9090165.	04/11/2025	SR of EEs	Published	<p>ERSs were cost-effective compared with (enhanced) usual care in most of the analyses. Ten analyses aimed to express the results by means of an ICER, out of which seven analyses showed that the ICER was below a given threshold, thus considered ERSs cost-effective compared with (enhanced) usual care.</p> <p>However, relatively modest health gains were reported, both in terms of natural health outcomes as well as QALY gains. For example, when comparing with (enhanced) usual care, the highest QALY gains reported—over a lifetime time horizon—were 79 QALYs per 1,000 persons.</p>	<p>Compiled economic evidence of ERS'. Presented outcomes of incremental effect used in EEs including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QALY • Steps per day • Level of walking • % participants active • Reduced anxiety • Reduced absenteeism • Disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) averted <p>No reporting of HCRU but could look at individual studies to assess this.</p> <p>Presents incremental costs of ERS' but not likely to need that information for our primary evaluation.</p> <p>Cost-effectiveness against a threshold – thresholds not reported in SR. So, statement of ICER being below threshold not appropriate unless parametrised threshold exists for incremental effect assessed.</p>
Health Evidence	Williams NH, Hendry M, France B, Lewis R, Wilkinson C. Effectiveness of exercise-referral	04/11/2025	SR	Published	<p>Exercise-referral schemes have a small effect on increasing physical activity in sedentary people. Results from five RCTs were combined in a meta-analysis. There was a</p>	<p>Focus on physical activity outcomes of interest to our research question. Presented economic evidence from 3 RCTs. One RCT collected data on hospital admissions, outpatient,</p>

	<p>schemes to promote physical activity in adults: systematic review. Br J Gen Pract. 2007 Dec;57(545):979-86. doi: 10.3399/096016407782604866. PMID: 18252074; PMCID: PMC2084138.</p>				<p>statistically significant increase in the numbers of participants doing moderate exercise with a combined relative risk of 1.20 (95% confidence intervals = 1.06 to 1.35). This means that 17 sedentary adults would need to be referred for one to become moderately active. This small effect may be at least partly due to poor rates of uptake and adherence to the exercise schemes.</p> <p>There was no statistically significant difference in anthropometric, physiological or biochemical outcomes between exercise groups and controls. Any improvement in these outcomes in the exercise group, particularly in the subgroup that reached the exercise target, was mirrored by similar improvement in the control group.</p>	<p>accident and emergency, and general practice services, but did not include them when calculating their cost-utility ratio. One RCT collected health service and participants' costs as well as costs of the exercise programmes and combined them in a cost-effectiveness analysis. Would be worthwhile assessing individual level EEs identified in this review to identify the HCRU impacts reported in them.</p> <p>References of interest: Isaacs et al., 2007 Munro et al., 2004 Stevens et al., 1998</p>
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Table 3: Summary of included primary evidence

Primary Research			
Aspect of Question explored	Study type	Date	Other Comments
Assessed physical activity and mental health/wellbeing	RCT of NERS	2012	Useful as assessment of effectiveness of NERS in Wales, although dated.
Assessed HRQoL and HCRU	Economic Evaluation of NERS	2013	Useful as economic evaluation of NERS in Wales, although dated.
Clinical Guidelines (CGs) of Physical activity: exercise referral schemes	NICE Public health guideline: PH54:	2014	Useful to define ERS in a UK-wide context.

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8. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

8.1. Conflict of interest

The authors declare they have no conflicts of interest to report.

8.2. Acknowledgments

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9. APPENDIX: Resources searched during Rapid Evidence Summary

A single list of resources has been developed for guiding and documenting the sources searched as part of Rapid Evidence Summary. Not all resources will be searched, depending on relevancy.

Secondary research resources <i>(Tailor the list according to the topic and potential evidence base, talk to stakeholder before proceeding with this type of search)</i>	Success or relevancy of the retrieval
Medical and health	
Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR) https://www.cochranelibrary.com/cdsr/reviews	Searched, nothing found
JBI (via OVID) (Subscription based service – WCEBC has a subscription)	Not searched, maybe relevant
NIHR Journals Library https://www.journalslibrary.nihr.ac.uk/#/	Searched, nothing found
Trip (TripPro can be accessed by an institutional based subscription based via institution, otherwise use Trip) https://www.tripdatabase.com/	Searched, results found
International HTA database (INAHTA-HTA) (for technology & intervention questions only) https://database.inahta.org/	Searched, nothing found
Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (ahrq.gov) https://www.ahrq.gov/research/publications/search.html	Searched, nothing found
CADTH Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health https://www.cadth.ca/	Searched, nothing found
PROSPERO https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/	Searched, results found
PubMed Filter by systematic reviews, reviews or meta-analysis once search undertaken https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/	Not searched, maybe relevant
UK Guidelines	
NICE The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence https://www.nice.org.uk/	Searched, results found
SIGN Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network (sign.ac.uk) https://www.sign.ac.uk/our-guidelines/	Searched, nothing found
Public health and social sciences	
Campbell Collaboration https://www.campbellcollaboration.org/better-evidence.html	Searched, nothing found
Epistemonikos https://www.epistemonikos.org/en/advanced_search https://www.epistemonikos.org/ (for the simple search)	Searched, results found
Health Evidence™ https://healthevidence.org/default.aspx	Searched, results found

The Guide to Community Preventive Services (The Community Guide) https://www.thecommunityguide.org/	Searched, nothing found
EPPI Centre Home (ioe.ac.uk) http://eppi.ioe.ac.uk/cms/	Searched, nothing found
3ie Development Evidence Portal 3ie (3ieimpact.org) https://developmentevidence.3ieimpact.org/	Searched, nothing found
Environment	
The Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (CEE) https://environmentalevidence.org/ CEE Database of Evidence Reviews (CEEDER) – Environmental Evidence https://environmentalevidence.org/ceeder/	Not searched, not relevant
Economic	
ScHARRHUD https://www.scharrhud.org/ (Innovative database aimed at improving access to health utilities evidence)	Not searched, not relevant
Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) Registry https://cevr.tuftsmedicalcenter.org/databases/cea-registry (database of cost-utility analyses on a wide variety of diseases and treatments)	Searched, results found
Additional resources searched (Add in any further resources that have been used, e.g. Scopus, HMIC, Social Care Online)	
Google Advanced Search https://www.google.co.uk/advanced_search	Not searched, not relevant
Google Scholar https://scholar.google.com/	Searched, results found
Google	Searched, results found

Health and Care
Research Wales
Evidence Centre

Canolfan Dystiolaeth
Ymchwil Iechyd a
Gofal Cymru

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